

Psalm 80

"Children of men"

All children of men are children of God.
They are, in truth, the highest among us.
In certain ways, the wisest.

For they know something
we have forgotten:

what truth feels like,
what it means
to be pure,
to be happy,
to be innocent,
to believe.

They are the highest among us,
closer to God.

So we should listen to them.

And yet we are the older ones.
The parents, the siblings, the teachers.

We must educate, must shape,
so that they become like us.

So it is determined.

And yet it is as if they were descending
to us from heaven on little stairways.

They still live over there,
in the eternal realm.

Only later do they cross the threshold
from the first heaven
into the outer circle

of pain and suffering.

The forests and the rivers.

The rain – the wind – the thunder.

Pain – loss – tearing apart.

The ones who are burning in the wasteland,
asking to be allowed to enter the heavens
but grateful to be permitted
to live within the ring of fire.

Then they are grown up.

And when I was a child,
I thought like a child,
felt like a child and
acted like a child.

Now that I am grown up,
I think like a grown-up,
feel like a grown-up,
act like a grown-up.

And as I am now grown up,
I realize:

I must help the children find their way
through the confusions of adulthood.

That they may stay on the path
to where we all came from.

For in the beginning we are love.

Therefore all children
will awaken in love.

And that is the shape of my heart,
to become a child of God again...

“from the New Psalms – The Way of the Open Heart”